

Psychosocial Determinants of Psychological Well-being of Indian Youth

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Psychological well-being (PWB) in youth is shaped by a complex interplay of psychosocial factors. This cross-sectional study investigated the role of social support, adverse experiences, and socioeconomic status in predicting PWB among 300 Indian youth (150 males, 150 females) aged 16-24 years from the Delhi-National Capital Region (NCR), India. Participants completed a demographic survey and the Psychological Well-Being Questionnaire for the Indian Population. Mean PWB was moderately high ($M = 178.34$, $SD = 25.11$). Males reported significantly higher PWB than females ($p < .001$). Having more friends and a friendly relationship with parents were strongly associated with higher PWB ($p < .01$). Experiences of bullying, physical abuse, sexual abuse, and suicidal ideation were linked to significantly lower PWB. ANOVA indicated small but significant effects of annual income and number of friends, while regression showed parental support and number of friends as significant predictors. Findings highlight the protective role of supportive relationships and the detrimental impact of abuse on youth well-being. Interventions should prioritize strengthening family and peer support systems to promote mental health in Indian youth.

Keywords: Psychological well-being, youth, social support, bullying, physical abuse, sexual abuse, suicidal thoughts

Psychological Well-being is rooted in Greek concept of eudaimonia, meaning, living well. Ryff (1989) defined Psychological well-being as, optimal psychological functioning, encompassing purpose in life, autonomy, personal growth, positive relationships, self-acceptance, and environmental mastery.

Dhanabhakyaam and Sarath (2023) reviewed classical theories of well-being, including Ryff's eudaimonic model, Diener's subjective well-being framework, and Seligman's positive psychology perspective., the review synthesized findings and explained psychological well-being as sense of contentment, happiness, and fulfilment in personal and professional roles, along with feelings of achievement, purpose, belongingness, and usefulness, while being relatively free from distress, dissatisfaction, or persistent worry

Kusuma et al. (2021) proposed that youth aged 16-24 are in transitional phase and experience significant psychological and social adjustment challenges affecting well-being. The World Health Organization (WHO) recognizes individuals aged 16-24 as youth, a group that is undergoing rapid biological, psychological, and social changes. In India, this age group forms nearly 27.2% of the population (Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation, 2022). A nation's progress is determined by its youth, making their

health and well-being a matter of national importance. Despite being a demographic dividend, Indian youth are also at higher risk of stress, uncertainty, unemployment, academic pressure, strained family dynamics, and limited access to mental health care.

Understanding the psychosocial determinants of psychological well-being among Indian youth is therefore vital. This knowledge is crucial to:

- Provide insights into protective factors (e.g., family support, social connections, economic stability) that enhance well-being.
- Identify risk factors (e.g., adverse childhood experiences, low socio-economic status, poor social support) that compromise well-being.
- Enable policymakers and mental health professionals to develop targeted interventions that strengthen resilience and promote positive mental health in youth.
- Contribute to designing age-specific, culturally relevant mental health strategies within India's growing population.

The increasing rates of mental health challenges, anxiety, depression, suicidal rates, academic burnout, and social challenges faced by young people have made understanding their psychological well-being an urgent priority. By highlighting the psychosocial factors of psychological well-being, this paper aims to inform evidence-based policy and interventions that safeguard the mental health of India's youth.

Numerous empirical studies have already highlighted the vulnerability of this age group. Hasan et al. (2024) demonstrated in Egypt that bullying had a significant negative effect on adolescents' PWB and self-esteem, while increasing psychosomatic symptoms such as headaches, sleep problems, and poor concentration. Stephen et al. (2023) pointed out similar findings reporting a significant negative correlation between bullying, self-esteem, and psychological well-being among adolescents in India.

In alignment with these findings, Dharani and Balamurugan

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We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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(2023) found that harassment and abuse considerably lowered Indian women's emotional stability and self-worth. Building upon this evidence, Kim et al. (2017) emphasized that emotional abuse exerts a more detrimental effect on psychological well-being than other forms of maltreatment. These findings emphasize how adverse psychosocial experiences disrupt both self-concept and mental health.

While abuse worsens well-being, social and environmental factors also play a significant role. Rajkumar et al. (2022) through a systematic review of rural Indian adolescents, reported high prevalence rates of depression (27%), anxiety (26%), suicidality (9%), and conduct problems (19%), with girls particularly vulnerable to social anxiety. Likewise, in a study in Hungary, Nagy-Pénczes, Vincze, and Bíró (2020) highlighted that socioeconomic status, health behaviors, and especially family and peer support have a strong influence on adolescent mental well-being. Their study also highlighted that girls reported poorer mental well-being than boys, suggesting gendered vulnerabilities.

Collectively, these studies point out that psychological well-being in youth is a multifactor construct, shaped by several psychosocial factors like abuse, bullying, as well as social and economic contexts like income and social support. However, most studies are either focused on adolescents or specific subgroups, with limited evidence directly addressing Indian youth aged 16-24 years as a distinct population. Given India's large youth demographic and the cultural diversity of psychosocial influences, there is a pressing need to systematically investigate the psychosocial determinants of PWB in Indian youth, thereby generating insights for targeted, culturally relevant interventions and policy planning.

The current study focuses on the impact of psychosocial factors, such as abuse, bullying, social support, and income, on the Psychological Well-Being of the Indian youth with the following objectives.

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the association between social support variables of perceived friendliness with parents and the number of close friends and psychological well-being (PWB) among Indian youth.
- To investigate the relationship between adverse experiences (bullying, physical abuse, sexual abuse, & suicidal ideation) and psychological well-being.
- To assess the effect of socioeconomic status, measured by annual family income, on psychological well-being.
- To identify the most significant predictors of psychological well-being when considering social support, adverse experiences, socioeconomic status, and gender together in a multivariate regression model.

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H1*: Perceived friendliness with parents and the number of close friends will positively predict psychological well-being.
- *H2*: Youth with adverse experiences (bullying, physical abuse, sexual abuse, suicidal ideation) will report lower psychological well-being than those without such experiences.
- *H3*: Annual Income will significantly affect psychological well-being.
- *H4*: Social support, adverse experiences, Annual Income, and gender will together significantly predict psychological well-being.

Method

Participants

The study included 300 participants (150 males, 150 females) aged 16-24 years, from class 11th, 12th, undergraduate and post graduate courses, recruited through convenience quota sampling from private and public schools and universities in the Delhi-NCR region. Recruitment was initiated by contacting students in the researcher's immediate community, who then referred peers meeting the inclusion criteria. Equal gender representation was ensured. All participants provided informed consent and were informed of their right to confidentiality and withdrawal at any point.

Research Design

A correlational research design was employed to examine the association between psychological well-being and selected psychosocial variables among Indian youth

Measures

Psychological Well-being Scale: The Psychological Well-Being Scale developed by Sisodia and Choudhary (2005) is a standardized scale on the Indian population. It consists of total 50-items. The Likert type items assesses overall psychological well-being across five dimensions: life satisfaction, efficiency, sociability, mental health, and interpersonal relations. The scale has strong reliability with test-retest reliability of .87 and Cronbach's alpha of .90. Validity evidence includes face, content, and criterion-related validity, with a coefficient of .94. The 50-item scale is rated on a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 indicates Strongly Disagree, and 5 indicates Strongly Agree. Summed scores reflected levels of psychological well-being.

Psycho-Social Determinants Questionnaire: A self-constructed questionnaire comprising 8 items was designed to assess the participants' socio-demographic and psychosocial background. These included gender, annual family income, perceived relationship with parents, and number of friends, history of bullying, physical abuse, sexual abuse, and suicidal ideation. Factors of experience of bullying, physical abuse, sexual abuse, and suicidal thoughts were framed as simple yes or no responses. Factors of annual income had five levels, Perceived relationship with parents has 3 levels (*Very Friendly*=1, *Moderate*=2, *Not Friendly*=3); number of friends (*Many*=1, *Few*=2, *None*=3). Based on the previous literature and observations of the researchers, these variables had been considered.

Handling Data and Cleaning: Data were examined for discrepancies, duplicate entries, and erroneous values were either corrected or eliminated before analysis.

Procedure

Participants were recruited from public and private schools and colleges in Delhi-NCR. They were informed about the nature of the study and asked to refer peers who met the inclusion criteria. Most participants were contacted in person, while a few were reached through WhatsApp. After obtaining informed consent, participants completed a demographic questionnaire consisting of 8 items and the 50-item Psychological Well-Being Questionnaire developed for the Indian population. Anonymity and confidentiality were ensured, and all ethical guidelines were followed.

Statistical Analysis

Post examining for discrepancies or duplicate entries data were analysed using IBM SPSS (2016) for Windows.

Descriptive Statistics: mean, standard deviation, frequencies, and percentages to summarise and present the demographic variables and psychological well-being scores.

Inferential Statistics: t-tests, one-way ANOVA, and Regression analysis.

Results

Table 1

Frequency Distribution of Demographic and Psychosocial Factors N=300

Factors	Category	N	%
Annual Income	10- 20 Lac	139	46.3
	21-30 Lac	55	18.3
	31- 40 Lac	40	13.3
	41- 50 Lac	28	9.3
	51 Lac up	38	12.7
Friendliness with Parents	Very Friendly	138	46
	Moderate	130	43.3
	Not Friendly	32	10.7
No. of Friends	Many Friends	118	39.3
	Few friends	177	59

Bullied	No friends	5	1.7
	Yes	131	43.7
Physical Abuse	No	169	56.3
	Yes	95	31.7
Sexual Abuse	No	205	68.3
	Yes	53	17.7
Suicidal ideation	No	247	82.3
	Yes	122	40.7
	No	178	59.3

Note. N= sample size; percentages rounded to one decimal place

Table 1 presents the frequency distribution of youth on various psychosocial factors. 46.3% of participants fall within the Annual family income range of ₹1020 lakh, with only 12.7% exceeding ₹51 lakhs. 46% participants reported having a very friendly relationship with their parents, while 10.7% described it as not being friendly with their parents. Most participants reported having many friends (39.3%), while 1.7% reported having no friends. Adverse Childhood Experiences were common, with 43.7% reported being bullied, and 31.7% experiencing physical abuse. 17.7% reporting sexual abuse. A whopping 40.7% reported having suicidal ideation at some point.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics of Psychological Well-Being (PWB) by Gender (N = 150)

Variable	Gender	N	M	SD	Std. Error Mean
PWB	Male	150	183.97	25.073	2.047
	Female	150	172.71	23.938	1.955
Life satisfaction	Male	150	35.61	7.197	0.588
	Female	150	33.91	6.957	0.568
Efficiency	Male	150	39.35	6.072	0.496
	Female	150	36.36	6.796	0.555
Sociability	Male	150	36.21	6.214	0.507
	Female	150	35.17	5.530	0.452
Mental Health	Male	150	34.13	7.116	0.581
	Female	150	29.11	6.354	0.519
Interpersonal Relation	Male	150	38.67	6.034	0.493
	Female	150	38.17	5.700	0.465

Note. PWB psychological well-being, M=mean, SD = standard deviation

Table 3

Independent Samples t-Tests for Mean Differences in Psychological Well-Being by Gender, Bullying, Abuse, and Suicidal Ideation

Variables	Group	Mean±SD	t (df)	p	SD
Gender	Male	183.97±25.07	3.98	<.001***	0.46
	Female	172.71±23.94			
Bullied	Present	172.85±24.71	-3.39	.001**	0.39
	Absent	182.59±24.66			
Physical Abuse	Present	172.14±25.22	-2.95	.003**	0.34
	Absent	181.21±24.6			
Sexual Abuse	Present	171.51±24.07	-2.2	.029*	0.25
	Absent	179.81±25.14			
Suicidal Ideation	Present	172.29±26.14	-2.2	<.001***	0.41
	Absent	182.49±23.57			

Note. N=300 M=mean; SD= Standard deviation; d = Cohen's d. Effect size interpretation follows Cohen (1988): small (.20), medium (.50), large (.80). *p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001

Table 2 presents descriptive statistics of PWB scores by gender. Male participants ($n = 150$) reported higher overall PWB ($M = 183.97$, $SD = 25.07$) than female participants ($n = 150$; $M = 172.71$, $SD = 23.94$). Across the PWB dimensions, males scored higher on life satisfaction, efficiency, sociability, and mental health, while scores on interpersonal relations were similar for both genders ($M = 38.67$, $SD = 6.03$ for males; $M = 38.17$, $SD = 5.70$ for females). Standard errors were small for all measures, indicating precise estimates of the means.

An independent-samples t-test, presented in Table 3, examined differences in psychological well-being scores based on gender, bullying experience, physical abuse, sexual abuse, and suicidal ideation

A statistically significant difference in psychological well-being scores between males $M = 183.97$, $SD = 25.07$ and females $M = 172.71$, $SD = 23.94$, $t(298) = 3.98$, $p < .001$, $d = 0.46$ was observed. Male participants reported higher psychological well-being than

female participants, with a small-to-medium effect size.

Participants who reported being bullied ($M = 172.85$, $SD = 24.71$), scored significantly lower than those who did not ($M = 182.59$, $SD = 24.66$), $t(298) = -3.39$, $p = .001$, $d = 0.39$, indicating a small effect size.

Participants who experienced physical abuse ($M = 172.14$, $SD = 25.22$) scored lower psychological well-being scores than those who did not experience physical abuse ($M = 181.21$, $SD = 24.60$), $t(298) = -2.95$, $p = .003$, $d = 0.34$. The effect size was small.

Participants who reported sexual abuse ($M = 171.51$, $SD = 24.07$) scored low psychological well-being than those without this experience ($M = 179.81$, $SD = 25.14$), $t(298) = -2.20$, $p = .029$, $d = 0.25$, representing a small effect size.

Participants who reported having suicidal ideation ($M = 172.29$, $SD = 26.14$) scored lower psychological well-being scores than those without suicidal ideation ($M = 182.49$, $SD = 23.57$), $t(298) = -3.52$, $p < .001$, $d = 0.41$, indicating a small effect size close to medium.

Table 4

Descriptive Statistics of Psychological Well-Being Scores by Annual Income (N = 300)

Annual Income Group	n	M	SD	SE	95% CI for M (Lower, Upper)	Min	Max
10- 20 Lac	139	179.06	26.34	2.23	174.64, 183.47	90	250
21-30 Lac	55	173.13	23.13	3.12	166.87, 179.38	116	232
31-40 Lac	40	170.10	22.75	3.6	162.82, 177.38	92	208
41-50 Lac	28	187	26.69	5.04	176.65, 197.35	138	237
51 lac Up	38	185.55	20.9	3.39	178.68, 192.42	133	235
Total	300	178.34	25.11	1.45	175.49, 181.19	90	250

Note. N= sample size. M= mean. SD= standard deviation

The descriptive statistics of Psychological Well-being by Annual Income, as presented in Table 4, highlighted that the income groups 21-30 Lac ($M=173.13$, $SD=23.13$) and 31-40 Lac ($M=170.10$, $SD=22.7$) reported lower psychological well-being scores. The Highest Income group 40-50 Lac ($M= 187$, $SD=26.69$) and 51 lac and above ($M= 185.55$, $SD=20.9$) reported the highest psychological well-being scores.

Table 5

One-way Analyses of Variance Predicting Psychological Well-being (N = 300)

Predictor	df	F	p	η^2
Gender	1, 298	1.07	.302	.004
Annual Income	4, 295	3.42	.009	.04
Friendly with parents	2, 297	15.09	<.001	.09
Number of friends	2, 297	7.24	.001	.05
Bullied	1, 298	11.48	.001	.04
Physical abuse	1, 298	8.70	.003	.03
Sexual abuse	1, 298	4.82	.029	.02
Suicidal ideation	1, 298	12.40	<.001	.04

Note: N= sample size, M= mean. SD= standard deviation. p values< .05, p< .01. Effect size interpretation per Cohen (1988). η^2 = eta squared.

A series of one-way analyses of variance examined demographic and psychosocial predictors of psychological well-being (see Table

5). Significant effects emerged for annual income, $F(4, 295) = 3.42$, $p = .009$, $\eta^2 = .04$; friendliness with parents, $F(2, 297) = 15.09$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .09$; number of friends, $F(2, 297) = 7.24$, $p = .001$, $\eta^2 = .05$; bullying, $F(1, 298) = 11.48$, $p = .001$, $\eta^2 = .04$; physical abuse, $F(1, 298) = 8.70$, $p = .003$, $\eta^2 = .03$; sexual abuse, $F(1, 298) = 4.82$, $p = .029$, $\eta^2 = .02$; and suicidal ideation, $F(1, 298) = 12.40$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .04$. No significant gender effect was found, $F(1, 298) = 1.07$, $p = .302$, $\eta^2 = .004$. Friendliness with parents showed the strongest association.

Hence, these findings suggest that adverse experiences (bullying, physical abuse, sexual abuse, suicidal ideation), Income, and social support (income, friendships, & parental relationships) are predictors of psychological well-being. Friendliness with parents showed the strongest effect, $\eta^2 = .09$.

Model summary: $R = .437$, $R^2 = .191$, Adjusted $R^2 = .161$, $F(14, 285) = 4.83$, $p < .001$. The regression model explained 19.1% of the variance in PWB; thus, the overall model was significant. Female participants ($B = -8.26$, $SE = 2.81$, $\beta = -0.165$, $t = 2.94$, $p = .004$) reported lower PWB scores compared to males

Participants who reported not having friendly relations with parents had significantly lower PWB ($B = -10.92$, $p = .002$) as compared to the reference group. Participants with no friends had significantly lower PWB compared to those with many friends ($B = -9.18$, $p = .008$).

Income group 4 (41-50 Lakh Per Annum) was associated with

Table 6*Multiple Regression Predicting Psychological Well-being Among Indian Youth(N=300)*

Predictor	B	SE	β	t	p	95% CI
(Constant)	186.54	5.62	-	33.18	<.001	[175.49, 197.59]
Gender(Female=1)	-8.26	2.81	-.17	-2.94	0.004	[-13.79, -2.73]
Income: Category 4	7.81	3.6	0.15	2.17	0.031	[0.69, 14.93]
Friendly with Parents: Not	-10.92	3.41	-.24	-3.20	0.002	[-17.64, -14.20]
Number of friends: None	-9.18	3.41	-.24	-2.69	0.008	[-15.91, -2.45]

Note. B= unstandardized regression coefficients, SE=standard errors, β =standardized regression coefficients. Confidence intervals (CI) are reported at the 95% level. Gender was dummy coded (male = 0, female = 1). Income categories, parental friendliness, and number of friends were dummy coded, with the lowest or most adaptive category serving as the reference group. Only statistically significant predictors from the full regression model are reported.

Significantly higher PWB compared to the lowest income category (reference), $B = 7.81, p = .031$.

Other variables, including bullying, physical abuse, sexual abuse, and suicidal ideation, did not significantly predict psychological well-being after controlling for other variables.

Summary of Hypotheses Testing

Regression coefficients supported Hypothesis 1, which stated that psychological well-being would be positively correlated with friendliness with parents and the number of close friends. Bivariate results confirmed Hypothesis 2, which predicted that young people who experienced adverse childhood experiences would report lower levels of well-being, but the multivariate regression did not support this; thus, H2 was partially accepted. Since only specific income groups displayed significant differences, hypothesis 3, which predicted a strong income effect, was also partially accepted. The regression model demonstrated a significant combined prediction by gender, socioeconomic status, negative experiences, and social support, supporting Hypothesis 4.

Discussion

Gender: A study conducted in Hungary by Nagy-Pénze et al. (2020) highlighted that socioeconomic status, health behaviours, and especially family and peer support strongly influence adolescent mental well-being. Their study showed that girls reported poorer outcomes than boys, suggesting gendered vulnerabilities. This was consistent with the present research findings, where females scored lower on efficiency and mental health parameters of PWB than males. The overall PWB in females ($B = 8.26, p = .004$) was lower than that of male participants.

Income: Income showed a partial effect on PWB. The lowest income group scored better on psychological well-being than the second and third highest income groups. The two highest income groups scored the highest on psychological well-being scores. These findings show the complex relationship between socio-economic factors like Income on psychological Well-being.

The complex relation of income with psychological well-being supports the work of Navarro-Carrillo et al. (2020) who found that more than the objective side of Socioeconomic factors (income, education, occupation), it was the subjective Socioeconomic factors, like how people perceived their status and education as compared to others, which better predicted psychological well-being than income parameters alone.

Social Support: Participants who reported having friendly relations with their parents and having many friends scored higher on PWB scores. Abubakar (2013) had similar findings, indicating that both parent and peer attachment play an important role in the identity formation and psychological well-being of adolescents in Kenya, irrespective of a disabling condition. The results emphasized the importance of social support through parental relationships and friendships in improving the psychological well-being of Indian youth, with gender and select income differences also playing a role. The results of this study were consistent with the literature, as good family relationships and friendships were positively associated with higher PWB (Tramonti et al., 2019).

Abuse and Suicidal Ideation: Mosley-Johnson (2019) reported that Adverse childhood variables were significantly associated with lower life satisfaction, lower psychological well-being, and lower social well-being. However, in the current study, bullying, physical abuse, sexual abuse, and suicidal ideation did not significantly predict psychological well-being after controlling for other variables. This points out that PWB is a dynamic interaction of individual subjective experiences. and the complex interplay of psychosocial factors on PWB.

Gender (female), low income, poor parent-child relationships, and lack of close friends significantly lowered psychological well-being. These findings further emphasize the multidimensional nature of PWB.

Implications of the Study

The consistent association between factors of social support and PWB points to a need to have interventions that encourage open parent-child relationships and create supportive community networks through workshops and meaningful engagements. Policy makers and Schools can promote peer support groups, group sports, and mentoring programs to cultivate meaningful relationships among youth, hence promoting PWB.

Limitations of the Study

The sample used convenience quota sampling in urban Delhi-NCR, which limits generalizability to rural populations or other regions of India. Data were self-reported; therefore may not be free from biases. The adverse experiences were assessed using simple yes and no categories, instead of a standardized tool or a detailed questionnaire. Relationships observed reflect associations rather than direct impacts, and the cross-sectional methodology limits drawing conclusions about causality.

Future Suggestions

A future research should employ a standardized adverse experience tool to investigate impact of psychosocial factors on PWB of Indian Youth. Additionally, a larger and diverse sample size may be used to investigate gender differences and mediating role of social support in PWB of Indian youth.

Conclusion

Findings emphasize the strong role of social support in PWB of this urban youth sample, whereas adverse experiences did not independently predict well-being after covariate adjustment. Bivariate analyses showed harmful effects of adverse experiences such as bullying, physical and sexual abuse, and suicidal ideation, though these factors did not significantly predict well-being when controlling for social support, income, and gender in the multivariate model. While adverse experiences significantly predicted lower PWB in unadjusted models, social support demonstrated stronger effects. This may indicate a buffering mechanism of social support, and merits further analysis with a larger sample to independently determine its contributions.

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Received January 20, 2026

Revision received February 5, 2026

Accepted February 10, 2026